

EFFECTIVENESS OF VOCABULARY EDUCATION THROUGH STORIES

Maxkamova Shaxlo Xasanovna

Tashkent State University of Uzbek language and
Literature named after Alisher Navai Uzbekistan, Tashkent,
maxkamovashahlo1403@gmail.com

Abstract: In this thesis, the problems of vocabulary development in students and various factors that interfere with the formation of this skill are described, different methods used by different teachers and their positive and negative aspects are evaluated. The importance of vocabulary is emphasized in three stages. All exams and tests are mainly based on vocabulary, potential employees are considered to be better the more vocabulary they have, and vocabulary is a source of commerce. It is known that the formation and activation of students' initial knowledge and motivation is one of the most important objectives in vocabulary acquisition.

English speaking students with slow vocabulary development cannot understand the text at grade level. These students may perform poorly on assessments in multiple domains and are at risk of being diagnosed with a learning disability. I know that vocabulary acquisition, semantic development, and word knowledge growth are currently being studied in many interesting ways. Therefore, the study presented here complements and extends these studies by introducing effective strategies for learning English vocabulary. This is an ESL classroom with the academic goal of accelerating ELLs vocabulary development.

Without vocabulary knowledge, neither language production nor language comprehension is possible. Therefore, increasing vocabulary knowledge is one of the most important requirements for language learning, and this increase in vocabulary knowledge is only possible when teachers adopt effective vocabulary teaching and learning strategies, which is the purpose of this paper.

There are many good reasons to use literature in the classroom. Here are a few:

- Literature is real data. It is a good idea to expose students to these unmodified language sources in the classroom because the skills they learn in dealing with difficult or unfamiliar language can be applied outside the classroom.

- Literature encourages interaction. Literary texts are rich in multiple layers of meaning and can be used effectively to discuss and share feelings and opinions.

- Literature increases the richness of language. Asking students to study advanced or non-standard examples of language (perhaps literary texts) increases their awareness of the norms of language use.

- Literature educates the whole person. By studying the values of literary texts, teachers contribute to the development of students' attitudes towards these values. These values and attitudes also apply to the world outside the classroom.

- Literature motivates. Literature is highly valued in many cultures and countries.

Therefore, students can feel a real sense of accomplishment by understanding these highly revered works of literature. In addition, literature is often more interesting than textbooks.

Literature is also diverse and short stories are often used in EL classes.

Some of its advantages can be mentioned. First, short stories are practical because they are long enough to be covered in one sitting.

Or two class sessions. Second, it is not difficult for students to work with short stories themselves. Third, short stories offer a variety of options to suit a variety of interests and tastes. Finally, short stories are suitable for all levels (beginner to advanced) and all ages. (students to adults) and all grades.

In fact, story selection is one of the most important roles of a teacher when using short stories to teach English. Short stories vary in length, so it is best to choose a short story that can be completed during class time. The brevity of the text is important for students because it lets them know that they can read, understand and complete something in English, which gives them a sense of achievement and confidence. In

addition to the length of the text, Hill mentions three main criteria when choosing a text:

- (1) the needs and abilities of the students;
- (2) the linguistic and stylistic level of the text;
- (3) the amount of background information required for a true appreciation of the material.

The importance of considering these criteria can be recognized by understanding that the vocabulary and sentence structure of the short story under study must be appropriate for the students' level. If your text is aimed at lower intermediate students, you should avoid stories that contain archaic language, slang, strange words, or sentences that imitate the speech of certain places, ignorant people, or foreigners. Also, very long sentences are difficult for students to understand. Students get bored without reading the work because they don't understand these sentences and words. Therefore, before teaching short stories, teachers must determine whether the text is readable.

One of the most effective ways to help students learn new vocabulary is to teach them unfamiliar words used in the text prior to their reading experience. Teachers should review the learning materials in advance and determine which words may be unfamiliar. These words should then be identified and discussed. It is important that teachers not only tell students what words mean, but also discuss those meanings. This helps students understand the meaning and implications of words. In addition, discussions give teachers feedback on how well students understand the words. Students should acquire the vocabulary in advance and then read the text. It is important for language learners to write down the words they learn or come across.

The vocabulary journal can be used as a reference both inside and outside the classroom. Once students master the target vocabulary, it becomes easier to remember or use.

Contextualization

Students learn how to use words in sentences by filling in the blanks, creating stories, and role playing.

Marking (tactile learning)

Students label various parts or objects in the classroom. This activity can be extended at home or nearby.

Personalization

This process is also called deep processing. Students imagine specific activities related to the target vocabulary. Students imagine they are throwing their bags. Vocabulary target = throw.

You can also ask students to think and say individually what freedom means to them.

Students develop vocabulary, read with specific objectives, predict from context, use context-relevant definitions, use key word skills, and use dictionaries. You will gain understanding, efficiency, problem solving, creativity and independent learning as you learn to use a variety of strategies including:

The teacher's role in teaching vocabulary is very important. Their first and foremost task is to find easy and interesting reading material for students. In any vocabulary lesson, students are expected to know the meaning of more words than the teacher teaches them. A new perspective on teaching vocabulary in large classes focuses on the development of language skills and contributes to the personal growth and independence of students first as language learners and then as human beings.

In conclusion, it can be said that using stories in vocabulary learning is effective and important.

REFERENCES

1. Collie J & Slater S. Literature in the language classroom. (5th ed.). Glasgow: Cambridge University Press, 1991.
2. Harmer, J. "English Teaching Experience". New York: Longman Publishing. 1991.
3. Stahl, S.. "Vocabulary Knowledge". New York: Casa Newbury. 2005.

4. Zimmerman, C.B. Vocabulary teaching methodology. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2007.
5. Widowson, H. Style and Literature Education, 1993.
6. Turdieva, R. (2022). Transformative Learning and Critical Thinking in Online Education. European journal of business startups and open society, 2(1), 90–93
Retrieved from <https://www.inovatus.es/index.php/ejbsos/article/view/224>
7. Turdiyeva, R. (2023). The significance of psycholinguistics in the process of language acquisition and teaching. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(24), 317–320. Retrieved from
<https://openidea.uz/index.php/idea/article/view/1982>
8. Strategies for assessing the effectiveness of an online education program R. S. Turdieva and G.R. Razzakova E3S Web of Conf., 413 (2023) 03003 DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202341303003>
9. Radjabova, J. (2023). The role of technology in ESL teaching. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 3(3 Part 3), 197–200. извлечено от
<https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/11746>
10. Radjabova Jayron Ikram qizi. (2023). Effective Online Method of Teaching English. Eurasian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, 19, 73–75. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejhss/article/view/3947>
11. M. Sh. Khasanova, N. B. Mirzayeva. Importance of CLT in teaching vocabulary to adult learners. E3S Web of Conf. 413 03017 (2023). DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202341303017>
12. Khasanova, M. (2023). Interactive methods of teaching English language. B international bulletin of applied science and technology (Т. 3, Выпуск 11, сс. 469–471). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10215652>
13. Yusupova, N. N. (2023). Pedagogik ta’lim klasteri muhitida aralash ta’limni qo‘llash texnologiyasi. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(19), 224–230. Retrieved from <https://openidea.uz/index.php/idea/article/view/1699>

14. Nasiba, M. B. kizi . (2023). Modern methods and approaches of teaching english. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(20), 218–221.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10055299>

15. Yusupova Nargiza. (2024). Analysis of technology and methods of using mixed education in teaching English. Innovations in Technology and Science Education, 2(17), 472–479. Retrieved from

<https://humoscience.com/index.php/itse/article/view/2369>

16. Yusupova, N. (2021a). Rolli o'yinlar vositasidan zamonaviy o'qitishda samarali foydalanish metodikasi: wide use of role games in modern teaching methods. Integration of science, education and practice. Scientific-methodical journal, 2, 115–122.

<https://scholar.google.com/scholar?oi=bibs&cluster=14643726307165109744&btnI=1&hl=ru>